

CONSUMER BEHAVIOR IN RELATION TO COSMETICS

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Abstract

Cosmetics are shown highlighted in trade not only in Brazil, but also worldwide. If previously there was little participation of the male audience in this segment, currently the scenario is different. The change in male behavior, the demands of modern society and the labor market for a better appearance, were the main factors that drove male demand for beauty products and services. The general objective is to understand and analyze male consumer behavior with cosmetics. The methodology used was a bibliographic, exploratory, quantitative research, with male consumers. The survey showed that 58% are concerned with appearance, 73% spend up to R \$ 100.00, 55% are concerned with quality, 57% buy from specialized stores, vanity is related to well-being 61% and 48% buy products to take care of the whole body.

Keywords: Consumer behavior, male and cosmetics.

1. . Introduction

The word cosmetic was predominantly associated with a single gender, that is, feminine. That did not mean that men could never use cosmetics. However, marketers recently coined the term male cosmetics, thus identifying special segments for specific products based on gender differentiation. Undoubtedly, men are becoming increasingly sensitive about skin care and appearance. Male consumers are giving greater importance to good looks and aspects of personal care to improve the health and well-being.

There are many differences between the female and male cosmetics market. Thus, companies had to adapt their marketing strategies to get them to buy their products. These adaptations affect all areas of mix marketing: product, communication, location and price.

Until the late 90s, beauty products for men were almost nonexistent on the market. They did not have a special space in stores and men strictly used the products in a utilitarian aspect. This market interested only a few brands because it was considered a niche. Only the L'Oréal group had the courage to launch itself in this segment in 1985 with Biotherm Homme. This brand is considered as the pioneer in men's cosmetics, leading the segment alone for more than 15 years, and is the first that dared to proclaim that men also need to take care of themselves, clean their skin, combining pleasure and well-being using creams , lotions and even anti-wrinkle creams (BLANCHIN; CHAREYRON; LEVERT, 2007).

The success of any business organization stems from the company's ability to understand and influence consumer behavior.

Walters (1974) provides this definition stating that a consumer is an individual who buys, has the ability to purchase, goods and services offered for sale by marketing institutions, in order to satisfy personal or domestic needs, wants or desires.

Schiffman e Kanuk (2000) consumer behavior is, therefore, the study of how individuals make decisions to spend their available resources (time, money and effort) on items

related to consumption. Includes the study of what, why, when, where and how often they buy and how they use products purchased products.

For ABIHPEC (Brazilian Association of the Personal Hygiene, Perfumery and Cosmetics Industry) and for the sector it defends, the year was also a year of renewal, with adaptations a market which appears increasingly competitive. Only in 2018 the industries of the entire industry launched more than 7,400 products for new consumers, according to a survey from Mintel. The sector generated 125.7 thousand jobs, an increase of 4.3% compared to 2017. Considering all distribution channels, such as wholesale and retail, franchises, beauty salons and direct sales, the sector totaled 5.4 million job opportunities generated in 2018, 1% more than in 2017 (5.3 million), an important number in a year of crisis (ABIHPEC, 2020).

The market remains competitive and aggressive, adding up to a billing in the consumer price of U \$ D 30 billion (ABIHPEC, 2020).

Brazil is the fourth largest global consumer market for personal hygiene, perfumery and cosmetics, with 6.2% market share and a total of USD 30 billion in consumer sales in 2018, according to a study by Euromonitor. The country is second only to the USA (18.3% with USD 89.5 billion); China (12.7% with USD 62 billion) and Japan (7.7% with USD 37.5 billion). In 2018 the second place was placed in the consumption of deodorants, perfumes and male products and the third in children's products, but the crisis brought a drop in the ranking for sun protection (third largest consumer in the world), hair products and oral hygiene (fourth largest). Bath products remained stable in fourth place, as well as makeup in fifth, but depilatories went to sixth. In skin products, Brazil remains stable as the eighth largest consumer market in the world (ABIHPEC, 2020).

The last CENSUS made in Brazil points out that, of a total population of 190 million inhabitants, 93.4 million are men, that is, approximately 49% of the total Brazilian population (IBGE, 2010).

The problem of this article is to observe the behavior of the male consumer in relation to cosmetics?

The general objective is to understand and analyze the behavior of the male consumer with cosmetics.

When examining the consumption of cosmetics, it cannot be ignored that it has traditionally been developed for female consumers, since hygiene products are considered as a pervasive element of women's consumption. However, changes occurred in the cosmetics market to the extent that men have become key consumers for various cosmetic companies (SOUIDEN and DIAGNE, 2009).

Being physically attractive means to have better opportunities to find a preferred partner, is related to the theory that our body and physical appearance play increasingly important roles in contemporary society (LAKSONO and PURWANEGARA, 2014).

With this new concern with appearance emerged the figure of the new man and led to the emergence of the metrosexual term. Resulting from the junction of the words "metropolis" and "heterosexual", the word metrosexual should be understood as the most recent concept to define the male consumer, young urban, who venerates vanity. Despite the sum of the terms, one should not be confused and understand that there is a direct connotation with sex (GARCIA, 2011).

2. Development of the article

2.1 Male Cosmetics

The word cosmetics is known to the human race in its beginnings. At the same time, the desire to look good and attractive to all individuals can also be identified as the first place in the hierarchy of needs for centuries.

According to the US FDA Food and Drug Administration, under the US Department of Health and Human Services, cosmetics are referred to for their intended use, as articles intended to be rubbed, spilled, sprayed or sprayed, introduced or applied to the human body, for cleaning, beautifying, attracting or changing the appearance. Among the products included in this definition are moisturizers, perfumes, lipsticks, nail

polishes, preparations for facial makeup and eyes, shampoos, permanent waves, colors for hair, dental and deodorant creams, as well as any material intended for use as component a cosmetic product (FDA, 2020).

Despite the fact that the cosmetic industry is traditionally associated with women; there is a growing demand for cosmetics by men. The cosmetics market for men's niche is growing rapidly and gradually is an important opportunity for all industry manufacturers.

As a result, men's appearance has become more prominent. In the past, if something went beyond deodorant and body wash, men could be ridiculed, but today the male consumer has a variety of products to care for and maintain his appearance. Souiden and Diagne (2009) claim that large cosmetic companies have created products dedicated to men, such as face creams, anti-wrinkle creams, tanning products, coloring products and toning gels.

The view of a man increasingly concerned with their body appearance shows up in daily life. The man of the 21st century is taking care of his health, well-being and his presentation, with that the attention with the body and mind has been more in demand (EUFRÁSIO e NÓBREGA, 2017).

The "new man", according to Bastos (2005) is concerned with vanity and beauty, he becomes even more vain than women and consume beauty products care and aesthetics.

The male consumer audience, previously shy and unrepresentative in the beauty market, today increasingly seeks aesthetic procedures in order to maintain a good appearance, a healthy image or an improvement in the quality of life (SANTOS et. al., 2018).

According to Franca (2006), some men today believe that being apparently well taken care of results in greater chances of jobs, and this at the same time gives them personal satisfaction generating a constructive image of themselves.

Then, a "new man" or "modern man" appears, the metrosexual, who confirms the new virility which ends up causing breaches of pre-established convictions of what it is to become a man (UTZIG, 2016).

Resulting from the combination of the words "metropolis" and "heterosexual", the word metrosexual should be understood as the most recent concept to define the male consumer who venerates vanity. Young men, with high wages to spend, who live or work in the metropolis, are classified as metrosexual, because that is where the best stores are located (OLIVEIRA and LEÃO, 2011).

2.2 Consumer behavior

According to Kotler and Keller (2006) The aim of marketing is to know and understand the customer so well the product or service fits him and sells itself.

The consumer currently assumes a fundamental role for most organizations, and its valuation guarantees good results. Consumer behavior is a matter of interest to those who wish to influence or change this behavior, which can be defined by Engel, Blackwell and Miniard (2005) as the activities directly involved in obtaining, consuming and disposing of products and services, including processes decisions that precede and succeed these actions.

However, consumer behavior is to know when, why, how and where consumers choose to buy / use a product or service. Both individually and as a group, it seeks to understand the buyer's decision-making process. Its object is to deeply understand people's behavior, needs, desires and motivations, Samara and Morsch (2005).

According to Richers (1984) consumer behavior is characterized by mental and emotional activities carried out in the selection, purchase and use of products and services to satisfy needs and desires.

For Solomon (2002) consumer behavior is understood as the study of the processes involved when individuals or groups, select, buy, use, have products or services, ideas or expectations to satisfy needs and desires.

The author Kotler (1998) explains that the area of consumer behavior studies how people, groups and organizations select, buy, use and discard products, services, ideas or experiences to satisfy their needs and desires.

It is understood that the consumer purchase decision process is highly influenced by internal and external variables, such a process is changeable and fickle.

Despite appearing to be something subjective, according to Kotler and Keller (2006) consumer buying behavior is influenced by several variables, as follows:

- a) Cultural: variables related to the values, perceptions, religion, ethnic groups and social class that the individual is inserted;
- b) Social: involving reference groups, family, social roles and positions;
- c) Personal: they reflect the particular characteristics of people, such as age, occupation, economic condition, lifestyle and personality;
- d) Psychological: the motivations, desires, perceptions that lead the consumer to choose a certain product or service, combined with his needs at that moment and the position (positive or negative) of the consumer in relation to the consumption choices.

Figure 1 - Factors that influence consumer behavior

Fonte: Adaptado de Kotler e Keller (2006)

3 Discussion / analysis of results

3.1 Methodology

Gil (2007) defines research as a rational and systematic procedure that aims to provide answers to the problems that are proposed. The research starts with a question or a problem with the use of the scientific process and aims to obtain a return or a solution (CERVO; BERVIAN; DA SILVA, 2007).

With regard to the nature of the research, the present study is an applied research, as it is based on the need to solve real problems, more or less immediate, and has a practical purpose (VERGARA, 2010).

Lakatos and Markoni (2010) bibliographic research covers all bibliography already made public in relation to the topic of study among them (newspaper, books, monographs, magazines and theses) and other publicly available means to contribute to the development of the research.

Exploratory research aims to develop and clarify concepts and ideals, providing greater knowledge about a subject.

According to Cervo, Bervian and Da Silva (2007), exploratory research does not require the elaboration of hypotheses to be tested in the work, restricting itself to defining objectives and seeking more information on a certain subject of study. Such studies aim to become familiar with the phenomenon or get a new perception of it and discover new ideas.

According to the method of approach, quantitative research aims to quantify the data and generalize the results of the sample to the population of interest (MALHOTRA, 2012).

As for the technical procedures for data collection used, research is named after a survey (survey or poll) and field research.

The survey method, according to Malhotra (2012) is a structured questionnaire given to a sample of a population and designed to provoke specific information from the interviewees.

According to Malhotra (2012) the questionnaire is a structured technique for data collection that consists of a series of questions, written or oral, that an interviewee must answer.

Field research is characterized by investigations in which, in addition to bibliographic and or documentary research, data collection is carried out with the person, using different types of research. FONSECA (2002).

3.2 Data analysis

An exploratory research was carried out from 02/01/2020 to 02/28/2020, applying a questionnaire through the google forms tool, with closed questions and a 5 point Likert scale, obtaining 67 answers, following the data analysis.

Regarding age 34% from 31 to 40 years old, 27% from 20 to 30 years old, 23% from 41 to 50 years old, 15% from 51 to 60 years old and 1% 19 years old or less.

The survey quantified 51% are married / stable, 42% single and 7% divorced.

Where you live 72% are from the east, 10% area south west zone 8%, 6% and 4% center north.

Graph 1 - Appearance

Source: Author (2020)

According to Graph 1, 63% are satisfied with their appearance and 58% consider themselves very concerned with their appearance.

How much you spend per month on cosmetics 73% up to R\$ 100.00, 24% from R\$ 101.00 to R\$ 300.00 and 3% from R\$ 301.00 to R\$ 500.00, the power is verified purchase up to R\$ 100.00.

Graph 2 - Criteria when choosing to purchase cosmetics

Source: Author (2020)

Graph 2 shows 55% are concerned with quality, 15% price, 13% brand, 11% medical indication and only 6% are influenced by friends.

Graph 3 - What are the channels used to purchase these cosmetics

Source: Author (2020)

Analyzing graph 3, consumers are more likely to go to specialized stores 57%, perhaps because they provide a wider range of products and perhaps even help from the seller, supermarkets 21%, internet 18% and 4% resellers. Regarding the valorization of a cosmetic, 69% consider the benefit, 13% price, 9% brand and 9% type of use.

Graph 4 - Vanity is related

Source: Author (2020)

Regarding vanity is concerned, 61% health, 22% and 17% personal hygiene become more beautiful, exemplified in Graph 4.

Regarding frequency and liking cosmetics, 40% often use products to care for their appearance and 36% are very fond of products that improve their appearance.

Graph 5 - If your income was higher than the current one, would you spend more on your appearance?

Source: Author (2020)

Consumer behavior is evident in Graph 5, where the income was higher than the current 79% said they would buy more compared to 21% who do not.

Graph 6 - Which part of the body would you invest in first

Source: Author (2020)

Graph 6 shows the concern with the vanity of the male consumer, 48% would take care of the whole body, 21% face care, 21% hair care and 7% beard care.

Graph 7 - Importance when buying a product to take care of appearance

Source: Author (2020)

Regarding the importance when buying the product to take care of the appearance, 61% quality, fragrance 13%, brand 9%, type of use 9%, 5% price and 3% indication.

Table 1 - Products by use

	Daily	Almost Every day	Three times a week	Once a week	Once a month	Never
Antisignals	7%	4%	10%		9%	69%
Corrective foundation on the face (makeup)	4%	3%	12%	3%	4%	73%
Conditioner	25%	12%	15%	13%	9%	25%
Cream anti-stain and acne	9%	6%	10%	6%	15%	54%
Hair treatment cream	13%	4%	16%	7%	9%	49%
Hand and body cream	18%	12%	9%	16%	13%	31%
Face cream	18%	15%	7%	9%	10%	40%
Creams beard modeling	9%	3%	12%	12%	9%	55%
Hair removal cream or wax	1%	4%	10%	6%	21%	57%
Deodorants	90%	1%	4%	1%	1%	1%
Exfoliants and masks	4%	7%	16%	10%	10%	51%
Do the nails	3%	10%	13%	24%	15%	34%
Fixative, gel or ointment for hair	24%	15%	13%	6%	7%	34%
Skin cleansing	6%	7%	21%	15%	6%	45%
Body lotion	18%	4%	12%	9%	10%	46%
Facial Mask	4%	7%	15%	7%	9%	57%
Oils	6%	1%	13%	10%	7%	61%
Perfumes and / or cologne	58%	21%	10%	4%	3%	3%
Ointment for hair	18%	6%	15%	4%	9%	48%
Beard Products	9%	15%	16%	7%	10%	42%
Lip balm	7%	9%	15%	3%	13%	52%
Sunscreen	18%	18%	22%	7%	12%	22%
Anti-oil soap	18%	4%	15%	9%	12%	42%
Bar soap	67%	1%	10%	4%	4%	12%
Liquid soap	36%	12%	10%	7%	7%	27%
Shampoo	66%	13%	9%	6%	3%	3%
Hair dye		4%	9%	3%	7%	76%
Hair treatment	3%	7%	10%	3%	7%	69%

Source: Author (2020)

Table 1 shows the use of products by male consumers, it appears that the most consumed products are: deodorants; perfumes and or cologne; bar and liquid soap and shampoo.

We have a new attitude of male consumer behavior in relation to products: conditioner; hand and body cream; do the nails; fixative, gel or ointment for hair and sunscreen.

A change in the habits of the male consumer with the products: face cream; skin cleansing; body lotion; beard products and anti-oil soap.

Some products are still not widely used by the male consumer: antesignals; corrective base on the face (makeup); anti-spot and acne cream; treatment cream for hair; shaving creams; waxing or cream removal; exfoliants and masks; face mask; oils; hair ointment; lip protector; hair dye and hair treatment.

4. Final considerations

It is concluded that the present study sought to describe the behavior of the male consumer in relation to cosmetics, together with a research investigating his habits and consumption factors.

From the data collected, interpreted and analyzed, we observed that vanity is related to people's image, how they want others to see them, such an image is often achieved by using these products.

The idea of body care is linked to a stereotype created by society that seeks at different times in human history to define what is seen as beautiful and ugly. However, even though vanity is seen as an act of consumerism and often exaggeration, it is also defined as an agent of self-esteem and quality of life, providing well-being.

The consumer is likely to consume more cosmetic products, if their income was higher, but this factor does not prevent them from being concerned with appearance, thus seeking product quality, the best brand, in addition most consumers buy in stores specialized, vanity is related to well-being, they often use products to take care of their appearance and they are very fond of products that improve their appearance.

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